

2015

APR-MAY

***Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education
Research Journal (AMIERJ)***

***(Bi-Monthly)
Peer-Reviewed Journal
Impact factor: 0.948***

V O L - I V I s s u e s : I I I

***Chief-Editor:
Ubale Amol Baban***

**ETHICS AND SUSTAINABILITY ISSUES: A CHALLENGE FOR FUTURE
MANAGEMENT PEDAGOGY**

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Abstract

In order to achieve sustainability we should incorporate moral values and ethics into the Management Education. The teaching of moral and ethical values that differentiate right action from wrong action and which makes us a perfect man should be the goal of sustainable management Education. Profit is essential for the growth of business enterprise. It is regarded as good measure of efficiency; however, it should be seen in value based context also. Management Education, which is based upon Values, will be an instrument which not only provides a professional knowledge of management but also a purpose in life. The societies across the globe are more integrated than ever before due to Globalization which results into free flow of trade and merchandise. There is a problem of difference in value's in countries but still there are some common shared values, those values should be identified and incorporated in national legislation and management teaching. Every year thousands of professionals including those who are practicing management comes to India in order to be truly guided by the Indian values and learning. One such person was APPLE's founder Steve Job. Efficient Management is Essentials for Prosperity of Society. Management Education for sustainability should ensure an environmentally sound and economically prosperous future

Introduction

Efficient Management is Essentials for Prosperity of Society. It improves living standard of the people at large. Efficient management leads to better economical production which helps in turn to increase the welfare of people [1]. On the other hand, Sustainability is the ability and capacity to endure. In context with human, sustainability is the long-term maintenance of well-

being, which has environmental and social-economic dimensions. It encompasses the concept of stewardship, the conscientious management of resource utilization.

Education which leads to sustainability is a lifelong learning process that results into an informed and involved citizenry having the innovative problem-solving skills, socio-scientific temper, and commitment to engage in responsible personal and cooperative actions. These actions will facilitate an environmentally sound and economically prosperous future. So the task of management education should also be to provide benefit for today but ensure its benefit for tomorrow in the form of prosperity both economically and environmentally.[11] Concept of triple bottom line and social entrepreneurship is helpful in achieving sustainability.

In Management class students should be taught importance of dealing fairly with others in a business context. The students learn community and participation by active involvement in their communities. He learns and understands the concept of equity through understanding the views of stakeholders and responding to their needs through Community and participation. The management student should be trained not only to go for profit making but also to judiciously utilize scarce resources and environment for the common benefit for all. So the task of management education should be to identify the common cultural and ethical values, which have universal implication, and also to include in its teaching program and also include conflict of laws and ethical values as well.

In order to achieve sustainability we should incorporate moral values and ethics into it. The teaching of moral and ethical values that differentiate right action from wrong action and which makes us a perfect man should be the goal of sustainable management Education. Management Education, which is based upon Values, will be an instrument which not only provides a professional knowledge of management but also a purpose in life.

Importance of Education for Sustainable Development

Education for sustainable development is based on an idea i.e sustainability require more than legal frameworks, financial resources and green technologies; it also needs us to change the way we think – change that can best be obtained through education.

It was in 1992 when the international community first recognized the role of education in achieving sustainable development, when participants at the Earth Summit which was held in

Rio de Janeiro by adopting Agenda 21. Chapter 36 of which talks about promoting public awareness and training. Since then, these policy ideas have taken shape, and educators around the world are seeking to ensure that their teaching incorporates the principles and values of sustainability. [3] increased and rapid changes at all levels as well as pressing local and global sustainability issues require rethinking of how knowledge is generated, transmitted and utilized and also how future decision makers and professionals are trained to address the challenging issues of sustainable development. As intellectual leaders and major contributors to the capacity development required for global transition to sustainability, institutions of higher education are expected to respond strongly and holistically to societal challenges. In order to do so, they must embark on the daunting task of transforming themselves and bringing about desired changes to society at large. The UN celebrated last decade as, UN Decade of Education for Sustainable Development.

Importance of Management

Efficient Management is Essentials for Prosperity of Society. It improves living standard of the people at large. Efficient management leads to better economical production which helps in turn to increase the welfare of people. Good management makes a difficult task easier by avoiding wastage of scarce resource. It increases the profit which is beneficial to business and society will get maximum output at minimum cost by creating employment opportunities which generate income in hands. Organization comes with new products and researches beneficial for society [1].

Management provides maximum utilization of scarce resources by selecting its best possible alternate use in industry from out of various uses. It makes use of experts, professional and these services leads to use of their skills, knowledge, and proper utilization and avoids wastage. If employees and machines are producing its maximum there is no under employment of any resources [1]. It gets maximum results through minimum input by proper planning and by using minimum input & getting maximum output; therefore, it helps in reducing brain drain.

Sustainability viz. a viz. Management Education

Education in its narrow and technical sense means the formal process by which society deliberately transmits its accumulated knowledge, skills, customs and values from one generation to another. [10] And if we talk about management it is also a knowledge, skill, art, science etc which is practiced since the time when people first started living in a group. In fact Management in all business and organizational activities is the act of getting people together to accomplish desired goals and objectives using available resources efficiently and effectively [1]. Of course management education is provided within a larger education system. On the other hand, Sustainability is the capacity to endure. For humans, sustainability is the long-term maintenance of well-being, which has environmental, economic, and social dimensions, and encompasses the concept of stewardship, the responsible management of resource use. It is a reality that we all are knowingly, unknowingly and everywhere are part of one type of the organization or other eg:- education system which include university system, government organization, industrial organization, member of society or citizen of state etc and even family though in strict sense it may not be included in definition of organization as we talk in management.

Since organizations can be viewed as systems, management can also be defined as human action, including design, to facilitate the production of useful outcomes from a system. This view opens the opportunity to 'manage' oneself as a pre-requisite to attempting to manage others. So management has a role to play for managing management education to achieve sustainability. Education for sustainability is a lifelong learning process that leads to an informed and involved citizenry having the creative problem-solving skills, scientific and social literacy, and commitment to engage in responsible individual and cooperative actions. These actions will help ensure an environmentally sound and economically prosperous future. So the task of management education should also be to provide benefit for today but ensure its benefit for tomorrow in the form of prosperity both economically and environmentally [3].

The management student should be trained not only to go for profit making but also to judiciously utilize scarce resources and environment for the common benefit for all.

Concept of Triple Bottom Line and Social Entrepreneurship is Helpful in Achieving Sustainability

The triple bottom line consist of social, economic and environmental factors i.e the "people, planet, profit". The phrase "the triple bottom line" was coined in 1994 by John Elkington, who was the founder of a British consultancy named "Sustainability". He said that the companies should prepare three diverse and separate bottom lines. It starts with "Profit" which is the conventional measure of corporate profit and the First "bottom line". The "people account" is the second bottom line which measure how socially responsible an organization has been throughout its working. The last is the company's "planet" which is the third bottom line to evaluate how environmentally responsible it has been. It aims to assess the financial, social and environmental performance of the corporation over a time period. Only a company that produces a TBL or triple bottom line is taking account of the full cost involved in doing business.[5].

On the other hand Social entrepreneurship is the work of social entrepreneurs. A social entrepreneur recognizes a social problem and uses entrepreneurial principles to plan, organize, and actuate a venture to achieve social change. Social entrepreneurship is about: creating business models which orbit around low-cost products and services to resolve social inequities. The understanding that social progress and profit aren't mutually exclusive has led to lots of social ventures [9]. While a business entrepreneur usually measures performance in profit and return on investment, a social entrepreneur on the other hand focuses on creating social capital. Thus, the main aim of social entrepreneurship is to advance social and environmental goals. Social entrepreneurs are generally associated with the voluntary and non-profit sectors. However, these two points may be the two extreme views, the focus of management education should be to take help from both of them, and the two concepts may be incorporated in management teaching with relevant adoption as may be required.

Importance of Ethics in business and finance

In context of financial system and fiduciary responsibility there is a use of the terms "obligation", "trust" and "confidence" which underscores a fundamental and long-recognised truth: ethics is the bedrock of successful financial intermediation and, by implication, of successful financial systems and market economies. The capacity of financial intermediaries to

make credible commitments to a certain number of rules and standards of behavior is the source of investors' trust and confidence – ethics makes trust possible. For example, while opting retail financial services, customers' belief that financial institutions are “ethical” i.e. they observe rules that protect customers' interests, this belief makes them ready to entrust these institutions with responsibility for managing their assets. Thus, the ability to credibly commend to ethical behaviour has always been a core business requirement for financial institutions. Recent developments in financial markets attest to the dangers of undermining this ethical foundation and to the heavy costs that are incurred when financial systems do not function effectively. [6]

Importance of ‘Management Education based on ethics’ for achieving sustainability in a Globalised world.

Ethics together with the issue of sustainable development has become the main principle which drives the whole ideological process which should be at the base of this great idea and cause. Economics, Ethics and Sustainable development are triple concepts representing three vast areas whose interconnection is now commonly acknowledged. The experts of each of these three areas see this interconnection through their own point of angle. Among all the points of views, ‘the principle of the common good’ seems to be the most potent binding link between the three elements. This principle requires that the global society be structured in such a way as to ensure that every human being can have the possibility to develop and achieve his full potential. Indeed, the sustainable development considered as a component of an integral human development and is based on three dimensions i.e. environment, economic and social.

Taking from the same concept in order to achieve sustainability the value and ethics based education is very important for the MBA students because of the fact that now this profession has impact not only in a domestic country but it has reached in international arena. The societies across the globe are more integrated than ever before due to Globalisation which results into free flow of trade and merchandise. Speedy communication and faster mode of transportation has brought the whole world very close. No country of world can claim to be self-sustained that it can solely cater all needs of its citizens because of the reason of competitive advantage among the nations.

Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ)

**(Bi-Monthly) Peer-Reviewed Journal Vol No IV Issues III
APRIL-MAY 2015 ISSN 2278-5655**

The emergence of global icons like, Madona, Shakira, Michael Jackson, Angelina Jolie, Shahrukh Khan, Lady Gaga, Britney, AR Rehman, , Amtabh Bachchan, Salman Khan, Kareena Kapoor, Sylvester Stallone, Arnold Schwarzenegger, David Beckham, Rooney, Kaka, Tiger woods, Michael Schumacher, Williams sisters, Sania Mirza, Rafael Nadal, Sachin Tendulkar, Steve Waugh, Wasim Akram etc. has created a huge fan following throughout the world. Among Indian celebrities Recently Kareena Kapoor also got her second wax statue along with those of Shahrukh Khan, Amitabh Bachchan, Salman Khan, and Amir Khan at Madame Tussaud museum, London. The lifestyle of these global icons inspires their fans which are in huge numbers.

The sporting events like NBA tournament, Football clubs which have international players in one club eg Manchester United, Barcelona, IPL cricket tournament, WWE wrestling, Tennis Tournament, Formula one races etc. are truly becoming international events where people watches sports icons irrespective of national feelings. Further as a result brands like Nike, Adidas, Pepsi, MTV etc associating themselves with these events and are getting acceptance everywhere. McDonalds, KFC, MTV, Coca Cola has acceptance across the globe and they are helping in integration of cultures and along them values as well [7].

There is an immediate need to change our priorities, to correct the forces that encourage material wealth over global welfare and justice, and to reinforce the fundamental values that form the basis of human civilization all over the planet – compassion and respect for each other and the natural environment, tolerance and solidarity, and the pursuit of peace. The Earth Charter is considered as a peoples' document. It provides an ethical framework equally applicable to guiding the choices of individuals, companies and states. The related concept that Rule of law must include the universal values which are common and also which are evolving through interaction of different cultures must be translated into appropriate and enforceable legal instruments dedicated to sustainable development. Essential principles, such as the polluter-pays i.e liability of who so is doing pollution and precautionary principles, should be fully recognized by international and national laws and regulate the activities of all sectors.

So the task of management education should be to identify the common cultural and ethical values which have universal implication and also to include in its teaching program conflict of laws an ethical value.

India should take a lead in value based ethical education because it is a place for learning values for professionals.

India from centuries has enlightened the world both from knowledge, values and which ultimately gave nirvana and spirituality. Every year thousands of professionals including those who are practicing management comes to India in order to be truly guided by the Indian values and learning. Daniel Kottke, who was Steve Jobs College and later the first employee of Apple inc in an interview with India Today discussed about the visit of him and Steve Jobs to India “Before he began his journey to becoming perhaps one of the greatest innovators of present time Steve Jobs started a journey to find his inner self in India. It was in 1970s, when Steve had just joined his first company Atari and was passionate to the philosophy of Nirvana. After going through some bestseller philosophical books he decided to visit India where the Kumbh Mela was going on. Kottke put together the first Apple computer in along with Apple co-founder Steve Wozniak in 1976.

The memories of the heady 70s that Steve spent in India are blurred as they didn't maintain any diary record and also did not have cameras as they were here to get away from materialism. The experience changed the thinking of Steve Jobs who returned as a Buddhist with a shaved head and whose faith in human intelligence and technology was strengthened while they visited Neem Karoli Baba, the well-known spiritual guru of that era.”[8]

Conclusion/Recommendation

Efficient Management practices are fundamental for the Prosperity of Society. It improves living standard of the people at large. Efficient management leads to better economical production which helps in turn to increase the welfare of people. Efficient management is the holistic management practice which includes sustainability blended with ethics. Education for sustainable development is based on an idea i.e sustainability require more than legal frameworks, financial resources and green technologies; it also needs us to change the way we think – change that can best be obtained through education.

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(Bi-Monthly) Peer-Reviewed Journal Vol No IV Issues III
APRIL-MAY 2015 ISSN 2278-5655

Ethics are the foundation upon which the legal, institutional, industrial, business and other facets of sustainable development should be built. It is absolutely essential to reassert basic ethical principles and values if we are to enjoy a sustainable and equitable world. While emphasizing on management education in order to achieve sustainability we should incorporate moral values and ethics into it. The teaching of moral and ethical values that differentiate right action from wrong action and which makes us a perfect man should be the goal of sustainable management Education.

Sustainable development requires changes to the content of education in the new century. Orienting education reform right from selection of teaching faculty in order to ensure that right people are selected who are well versed not only in subjective knowledge but also have ethical and moral standing. We can start from campus building, i.e. their construction on green technology, rain water harvesting, fine on litters etc so that good habit can be uncultivated in the students. The attention should not only to increase only in number of legislation to curb unfounded practices but to create Management professionals whose inner voice also guide their actions.

As we know that management helps in raising standard of living of people through various means and also help in efficient and effective utilization of resources therefore in order to achieve prosperity in underdeveloped areas entrepreneurship should be promoted, which will also helps in reducing brain drain through development of that area. India from centuries has enlightened the world both from knowledge, values and which ultimately gave nirvana and spirituality, so it should come forward and take lead.

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Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ)

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APRIL-MAY 2015 ISSN 2278-5655

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